

PROGRESS OF RESEARCH

AUGUST 1967 to MARCH 1968:

Participation in Iran on archaeological excavations at Hush-i-Jan and Siraf, and on the study of the finds enabled me to gain additional archaeological experience and a considerable background in Islamic archaeology.

APRIL 1968 to AUGUST 1968:

A preliminary study of the documentary material was carried out at Oxford.

AUGUST 1968 to APRIL 1969:

Survey in Southern Iran as well as subsidiary study in Teheran was undertaken. The survey comprised an intensive investigation of the area and routes from Istalard and Shiraz to Sirjan and Ras, a reconnaissance of Persian Seistan, and a study of Islamic sites discovered by Mr. W. H. Sumner in the Kur River plain North of Shiraz. The Persian Gulf coast was investigated from Jask to Qalat, and the islands of Kish and Hormuz were briefly visited.

MAY 1969 to JULY 1969:

Further research was carried out at Oxford on documentary materials.

AUGUST 1969 to APRIL 1970:

Delays in obtaining my permit for renewed survey as well as that for excavation at the site of Sirjan (discovered in 1968), a series of illnesses, and a fall from my motorbicycle have permitted only ¹² twelve days of survey in the Bushehr Peninsula ~~and~~ near Siraf, + near B. Abbas.

APRIL 1970 to MAY 1970:

Excavations ^{will} ~~will be~~ undertaken at Sirjan, financed by the Stein-Arnold Fund of The British Academy, The British Institute of Persian Studies, and the Mayerstein Fund of Oxford University.

JUNE 1970 to SEPTEMBER 1970:

Since the weather does not permit reconnaissance work on the Persian coast, the study of the pottery so far recovered, and the section in my thesis on the items of trade will both be completed during this period.

Handwritten notes: a drawing for the report on the Siraf excavations, the complete Siraf - the area

PREVIOUS FINANCIAL SUPPORT

My present grants have both been renewed up to the maximum extent of tenure, and expire in June and September 1970. In the previous years my research grants have been:

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1967-1968:

The Department of Education and Science - for travel and living expenses. . . . £ 700

£ 700

1968-1969:

The Department of Education and Science - for travel and living expenses. . . . £ 1,150

The British Institute of Persian Studies - for the purchase of a Land Rover. . . . £ 600

+ BIPS

£ 400 / £ 1,750

85
22

Handwritten notes: Re Siraf Fellowship for work at Siraf

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1969-1970:

The Department of Education and Science - for travel and living expenses. . . . £ 1,200

The British Institute of Persian Studies - for the purchase of a motorbicycle and research expenses £ 450

£ 1,650

44
56
82

The Siraf Fellowship Fund of The British Institute of Persian Studies - for work at Siraf

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1) JUNE 1970 - SEPTEMBER 1970

Preparation of a report on the excavations at Sirjan, and completion of ~~the~~ ^{research} the historical section of my work on the items of trade.

PROJECTED RESEARCH

MARCH

2) October 1970 to ~~SEPTEMBER~~ 1971-Completion of archaeological survey of Islamic sites in Southern Iran (begun 1968-1969) along the following routes:

- a) The Persian Gulf coast from Qalat to the border of Khuzistan.
- b) The remaining Persian islands in the Gulf: Qeshm, Larak, Henjam, Honderabi, Lavan, and Kharg.
- c) The valleys behind the coast between Siraf and Lar.
- d) The routes from Bandar Abbas to Sirjan and Bam.

16 pp

3) ~~SEPTEMBER~~ 1971 to OCTOBER 1971-Final preparation of results in Oxford, ~~and presentation of thesis.~~

Note: April I intend to find out about this period associated

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 3 1/2
 4 1/2
 5 1/2
 6 1/2

140
 52
 700

DETAILS OF FUNDS REQUESTED
MINIMUM BUDGET

AMOUNT REQUESTED: £ 1,100.

Transportation-

- (1 1/2) Insurance on Land Rover and motorbicycle £ 49
- (1 1/2) Land Rover-calculated on the distance of 35,000 kms. travelled in 1968-1969:
- (1 1/2) Petrol £ 197
- (1 1/2) Oil £ 25
- (1 1/2) Motorbicycle-petrol and oil for 2,000 kms. £ 5
- (1 1/2) Maintenance and Repairs £ 200

£ 476

Research Expenses-

- (1 1/2) Pottery-transport and storage £ 30
- (1 1/2) Photographs 65
- (1 1/2) Drafting 20
- (1 1/2) Recording 34

£ 157

Living Expenses-

- (1 1/2) For one year-October 1970 to September 1971 . . . £ 550
- (1 1/2) Medical Insurance £ 7
- (1 1/2) Medical expenses £ 10

£ 567

TOTAL £ 1,200

72

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2 route amounts on the excavations themselves found of the excavations recording were in the area

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L) June 1970 to September 1970-Preparation of a report on the excavations at Sirjan, and completion of the historical section of my research on the items of trade.

3

I intend to spend two months assisting on the excavations at Siraf, and the remainder of the period of the excavation continuing survey in the area.

June 1970

Handwritten notes at the bottom of the page, including the phrase "The report to be submitted to all the staff of the organization" and other illegible text.

EXPLANATION OF RESEARCH

Project is
My research ~~is directed towards doctoral thesis~~ entitled:
"Archaeological and documentary material for the history and mechanisms
of commerce in Southern Iran from the seventh century to the ~~end~~^{end} of
the Portuguese. *period*"

The commercial importance of the area in historic times, until the development of the route to the East around the Cape of Good Hope, is well documented. A succession of major port sites on the North shore of the Persian Gulf, such as Siraf, Kish, and Hormas, played a major role in the transshipment and distribution of Far Eastern and Indian spices and other commodities to the Middle East and Europe, as well as participating in Indian Ocean and local commerce. These ports ranked among the richest in the world, but the reasons for their size and for the rise and decline of each in succession have not as yet been adequately explained.

The archaeological field work for this research consists of an intensive survey of the area bordering the North coast of the Persian Gulf and including the Iranian islands in the Gulf. Thanks to grants over the last two years from The British Institute of Persian Studies, I am equipped with a Land Rover and a motorbicycle to aid in the efficient coverage of the tracks in this difficult country. All sites investigated are recorded in terms of location, dimension, character of habitation, and resources, and a large sample of artefacts is collected from the surface. Almost 700 sites of all periods have been so far examined in this manner. After study the material from these will be deposited in the excavation museum at Siraf. Standing monuments, and especially all inscriptions, are being fully recorded. The prehistoric pottery is being studied by Miss Martha

Prickett of Harvard University and Mr. W. N. Sumner of The University of Pennsylvania.

The Southern part of Iran, and more particularly the coastal areas of the Persian Gulf and the islands, are specially suited for the type of intensive survey I am undertaking. Since the area is impoverished today, present settlement is small and rarely masks older material. Natural disasters and constant insecurity have necessitated the frequent abandonment of village and city sites. In addition, movement has been facilitated because settlement has been possible even in waterless areas by the use of cisterns to collect storm water run off.

current research page 2

The ceramic, glass, and other archaeological materials which are collected in this survey can now be dated fairly closely by reference to the artefacts recovered from the stratigraphic excavations at Siraf

~~Special attention has been paid to identifying the place of manufacture of distinctive types of pottery and glass. In addition, maps are being prepared to show the trade of pottery from its place of manufacture.~~

Siraf + Dabki
Deh

The excavations on the kilns at Siraf have clearly demonstrated that certain types of characteristic pottery were produced on this site. The excavations at Sirjan in the south may be expected to identify conclusively the range of the pottery produced in its kilns. In addition, in the last two years eleven separate kiln sites have been located in different regions.

The distribution from all these kilns gives an illuminating picture of the local trade in ceramics. The direction of long distance trade is demonstrated in the distribution of pottery, glass, and porcelains identified as originating in Mesopotamia, the Levant, or the Far East. An attempt is also being made to identify the sources of steatite found in abundance on many sites. Through mapping the distribution of oyster middens and by

types were
the large range of the pottery produced in the last 3 years

1970

to Mesopotamia

Further useful material has emerged on trade in building stones

the

examining intermingled or associated pottery and glass, the location and extent of ^{the pottery} ~~the~~ industry is being illustrated at different periods.

This archaeological work is by no means a substitute for documentary research. By studying the works of the Islamic geographers and travellers, and those from China and Europe, as well as the Portuguese papers of the colonial period, an understanding of the perishable commodities of trade, of the importance of individual towns, and of the routes taken between them is emerging. However, the archaeological material is most significant in that it provides a quantitative assessment of the size of sites, of the directions of trade, and of the relative importance of different routes, none of which are more than hinted at in the frequently contradictory historical record. By combining archaeological and historical material, a picture is being produced of the economic and political mechanisms of mediæval trade in this commercially important area.

The archaeological material gathered so far indicates a striking concentration of coastal settlement by period. For example, ^{the Helwan survey indicates that} within 50 kms. of Siraf there is a string of large and contemporaneous sites occupying in total more than three times the area of the major site. However, occupation has been very much reduced in this region at all later periods. The Dashehr Peninsula too, has many Sassanian and very early Islamic sites, three of which measure over 1 km. square. Yet the area seems to have rapidly sunk from this great prosperity, since there is very little settlement between the 9th and 15th centuries A.D.. This would seem to suggest that the records of families migrating from one city to another as the trade centres shifted might represent a major movement in population.

(+) In investigating the historically attested trade routes, it has been found that on the Iranian plateau virtually no pottery or glass was traded

Honorary.

route from Shiraz to Bam through Siraf

along the Shiraz-Siraf-Bam route which figures so prominently in the Islamic geographers' accounts of the overland route to Seistan and the Indus. These three cities are contained in separate, scarcely overlapping areas within which fine pottery was distributed from kilns situated near Istakhr, at Siraf, and at an unknown site near Bam or in Persian Seistan.

traded long distances!
On the coast however, ~~long distance trade in large quantities of pottery~~ *here* is attested. Even items of such low value as the domestic coarse ware

from the Siraf kilns were traded to Minab, 500 kms. down the coast, while storage jars reached as far as East Africa. *from which the long jars*

~~glazed pottery from Mesopotamia was traded in large quantities throughout the Persian Gulf and adjacent areas, yet little reached the Iranian plateau.~~

*However very little of this pottery was traded inland across the Zagros.**
Similarly, since the coming of Islam Far Eastern pottery and porcelain are found in large quantities in the warm lands around the Persian Gulf.

add AB

However, until the 14th century A.D. very little penetrated further inland. The city sites of Siraf, Kirman, and Istakhr are the only mounds on the southern plateau with Far Eastern pottery antedating the 14th century A.D.. Instead, the Chinese ceramics found in such quantities at Siraf and Kish were shipped to Mesopotamia. From the 14th century A.D. there is a significant change in the pattern, and *fairly few* sites on the southern plateau have been recorded with 14th to 16th century A.D. celadon or blue and white. By this period it seems that the economic hinterland of the major Persian ports was shifting from Mesopotamia and the West to the Iranian plateau.

~~My extensive discoveries of oyster middens, frequently mixed with Islamic pottery from the earliest period onwards and associated with sites even on the most barren parts of the coast, indicate the considerable economic importance of this industry. Although they are scarcely mentioned by the Islamic sources, pearl exports to the East are cited in foreign~~

accounts, both Chinese and European. ~~These accounts also stress the importance of the export of horses from the Persian Gulf to India, and suggest the possibility that the ports on the Persian Gulf (of which those on the northern shore were always the most important) to some extent traded their own products to the East, rather than merely acting as trans-shipment and distribution points, as has hitherto been assumed. In this way the Persian Gulf, together with East Africa, played some part in actually generating and financing the spice trade. To be specific, pearls and horses from the Persian Gulf, and ivory from East Africa, which were in demand in India and the Far East, were traded for oriental products and spices. The manufactured goods which the inhabitants of the Persian Gulf~~ lacked, such as pottery and glass, were to some extent supplied from Mesopotamia and the West in return for the spices obtained from the sale of Persian Gulf products further East. Since these Western and Levantine products were in little demand in the spice producing East, the direct shipping of spices to the Levant was, as the Egyptian ^{GENIZA} Jewish records show, mainly financed by the export of precious metals. However, by medium of the indirect trade through the Persian Gulf, spices could flow Westward, financed by the export of manufactured goods to the Gulf area. This does, I believe, make some contribution to the problem which has vexed so many scholars, of how the spice trade was financed without a considerable drain of precious metals from the Mediterranean and Arab world.